

THE STUDY OF THE INTERFACIAL REACTION IN TITANIUM-BASED MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Interfacial reactions have been investigated in Titanium-based matrix composites. It has been found that there is a non-stoichiometric interface formed around each TiC particle. The relation between reaction layer and interfacial layer width is also discussed.

INTRODUCTION

Designs for advanced aircraft and aerospace vehicles are calling for low-density materials, which is with high strength and modules at high temperatures. TI-15**alloy is useful composite material, which is receiving much attention lately. During the consolidation of a composite, interaction can occur between matrix material and TiC particle. It is important to understand these reactions, because their products can critically influence the engineering properties of the composite material.

Here is reported that distribution of carbon concentration in TiC particles near grain boundary has been investigated. The mechanical properties of this material will have presented in other paper. It is noted that some studies [1] have examined the reaction in annulus of the TiC particles with EELS and diffraction measurements, but the distribution of carbon concentration in annulus of TiC particles has not been examined previously.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

The composites contained 10% by volume of TiC. The samples were heat treat at 800°C and 1000°C, respectively for 1 h and air cooled. The samples for TEM were prepared by diamond cutting of thin slice, grinding and polishing to form about 50µm thick disks. The samples were then dimpled from one side just to perforation. This was followed by cold-stage ion milling at 5kV and 2mA gun current at 12 degrees tilts for several hours.

The samples were examined in PHILIPS CM12 transmission electron microscope equipped with Gatan-666 parallel detection spectrometer (PEELS). The incident electron beam energy during all measurements in this study was 100 kV. Care was also taken to operate at specimen thickness

such that multiple inelastic scattering events were not substantial and under diffracting conditions to minimize anomalous effects due to the orientation dependence of inelastic scattering.

RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

Fig.1 and Fig.2 expressed the carbon distribution of particles TiC at 800°C /1h and 1000°C /1h, respectively.

Fig.1 800 °C/1h air cooling (D represents the relative distance from the boundary of TiC particles)

Fig.2 1000°C /1h air cooling (D represents the relative distance from the boundary of TiC articles)

The electron energy loss spectra (EELS) were obtained from the annulus of TiC particles. Inspection of the spectra enables determination of carbon concentration for each area probed via the expression (1)

$$\frac{\text{Ti}}{\text{C}} = \frac{I_{\text{Ti}}(\beta, \Delta E) \cdot \sigma_{\text{Ti}}(\beta, \Delta E)}{I_{\text{C}}(\beta, \Delta E) \cdot \sigma_{\text{C}}(\beta, \Delta E)} \quad (1)$$

Where, for a given collection angle β and energy window ΔE , after the edge, $I_{\text{Ti}}(\beta, \Delta E)$, and $I_{\text{C}}(\beta, \Delta E)$ are the area under the titanium and carbon edge after background subtraction, respectively. $\sigma_{\text{Ti}}(\beta, \Delta E)$ and $\sigma_{\text{C}}(\beta, \Delta E)$ are the partial ionization cross-section for titanium and carbon under the experimental conditions.

The carbon concentration for each area (effective spot size is less 10 NM and the distance of adjacent points is 20 NM) and they were display in Fig.1 and Fig.2. It has been found that there is different distribution of concentration of carbon at 1000 °C/1h and 800°C/1h. The higher temperature the samples are treated, the wider the interfacial layer is. The generation of non-stoichiometric TiC is of course evidence. There has been a considerable interaction between the matrix and TiC particles. The reaction zone in the TiC particles could be generated either by the diffusion of C from the particles or by diffusion of Ti into TiC particles.

There is clearly the need for further work in this field in order to control (or optimize) the width of reaction zone produced. The reaction zone is controllable by the heat treatment schedule.

REFERENCES

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